

Figure 1: US-ELTP exhibit at AAS Meeting #242 in Albuquerque, New Mexico, with staff from the three partners. Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA

Update on the US Extremely Large Telescope Program

Lucas Macri and the US-ELTP team

The US Extremely Large Telescope Program (US-ELTP) is a joint endeavor of NSF's NOIRLab and the organizations building the Giant Magellan Telescope (GMT) and Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT). It was ranked as the highest ground-based priority by the community in the Astro2020 Decadal Survey report, *Pathways to Discovery in Astronomy and Astrophysics for the 2020s*. The US-ELTP system will provide astronomers in the US with nationally funded access to observing time on both the Giant Magellan Telescope in the southern hemisphere from Chile and the Thirty Meter Telescope in the northern hemisphere.

The US astronomical community will be able to use the US-ELTP system to observe objects anywhere in the sky and carry out transformational research on topics ranging from the search for life outside the Solar System to the nature of dark matter and dark energy. With their complementary designs and a diverse set of instruments, the two next-generation telescopes will offer great synergy with each other as well as other facilities in space and on the ground. The 50% sky overlap between the telescopes will facilitate observations of the most interesting objects in the sky with both observatories. Being situated in substantially different time zones on

the globe will allow the two telescopes to observe astronomical phenomena for longer spans of time — which is important for studying rapidly changing objects.

The role of NSF's NOIRLab is to provide the end-to-end system for proposal submission and evaluation; generation of observing programs for adaptive, integrated scheduling; operation of robust automated standard data reduction pipelines; data curation; and support of a data science platform, based on the heritage of its efforts for the Gemini and Rubin Observatories and the Community Science and Data Center.

Our team had a strong presence at the summer AAS in Albuquerque, where our booth was well attended. NOIRLab's Communications, Education, and Engagement Service worked with our US-ELTP partners to develop a traveling exhibit that has already been deployed at the fall meetings of SACNAS, SHPE, and NSBP. We are also proud to celebrate the launch of the new US-ELTP [website](#), which will continue to grow over the next few months. As this article goes to press, we are looking forward to our jointly organized [meeting](#), "ELT Science in Light of JWST" to be held at UCLA on 11–15 December. NOIRLab's US-ELTP Project Scientist (Eric Peng) is a co-chair of the SOC and a member of the LOC, while our Community Engagement Scientist (André-Nicolas Chené) is a member of the LOC. This will be the first in a series of three meetings on the topic, with the next one planned for early June in Japan and the last one to be held in Germany sometime during fall 2024.

The NSF provided \$15.3M in one-year [awards](#) to the US-ELTP in late September 2023, to support further design and development of advanced optical technologies and user services. The NOIRLab team recently met with the newly appointed Interim Division Director of the Division of Astronomical Sciences, Dr. R. Chris Smith, and with various Program Officers in the Division to provide updates on our efforts and discuss upcoming milestones. As this article goes to press, the NOIRLab team is working towards a Conceptual Design Review to be held at the end of 2024, while the telescope teams are planning for Final Design Reviews. Around the time the

Figure 2: NOIRLab's US-ELTP team members conducting a scope workshop in Hilo. From left to right: Eric Peng, François Pradeau, Steven Berukoff, Mike Fitzpatrick, Marie Lemoine-Busserolle, André-Nicolas Chené. *Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA.*

NSF awards were announced, our GMT partners celebrated the [casting](#) of their seventh primary mirror segment at the University of Arizona's Richard F. Caris Mirror Lab. Meanwhile, over 90 of the TMT primary mirror roundels have been polished, and their fabrication continues to accelerate with the [expansion](#) of facilities dedicated to this effort.

The members of NOIRLab's US-ELTP technical team are holding regular in-person and frequent Zoom workshops to further develop the design of the software and user services that will enable US community access to the ELTs. This critical work includes refining requirements and their traceability, defining processes and systems to support them, and identifying key risks and challenges ahead.

The NOIRLab US-ELTP team recently welcomed François Pradeau, our Software Architect. He is responsible for establishing and improving the scalable and extensible architecture of the US-ELTP user services platform. François has over 25 years of experience in the software and data engineering world, working on a wide range of products for different industries. We bid farewell to Tim Sacco, who started an LSST Discovery Alliance Catalyst Fellowship at the University of Arizona's Department of Sociology. Before departing, Tim helped put together a tiger team of sociologists to review and make suggestions for the next release of the [US-ELTP Toolkit of Collaborative Practice](#).